

Developing a Machine Learning Model for Detecting Job Burnout During the COVID-19 Pandemic Among Front-line Workers in Kuwait

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Abstract- During the COVID-19 pandemic, front-line personnel worldwide had tremendous psychological stress compared with the general population. High mental stress may lead to job burnout. This paper starts with gathering a job burnout dataset from medical staff and police officers working in Kuwait during the COVID-19 pandemic using a web-based Arabic version of the Maslach Burnout Inventory questionnaire. The gathered dataset shows that there are elevated burnout rates among the front-line personnel dealing with COVID-19 patients. It utilizes machine learning techniques including AnDE Bayesian, JChaid* decision tree, SVM margin-based, ForestPA Decision forest, and DMLP to predict the presence of job burnout. Then, we present efficient feature subset selection approaches using several metaheuristic methods such as Bat, Cuckoo, PSO, GWO, and CGWO to select the most competent features. Experiments showed that reducing the number of features allows for a better understanding of the underlying model used to make predictions. Results also support the adaptation of deep learning architectures in social sciences when data is relatively small. These results may considerably help to screen out the front-line workers at high risk for job burnout.

Keywords— Job Burnout; COVID-19; Chaotic Grey Wolf Optimization; Machine Learning; Data Mining.

I. INTRODUCTION

The coronavirus epidemic – known as 2019-nCoV, or COVID-19- first broke out in December 2019 and has rapidly spread in China and all over the globe. COVID-19 spans more than 222 countries and territories, with the current tally at about 200 million confirmed cases, and has claimed more than 4,371,673 lives [1,2]. The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in increased levels of panic and anxiety among people worldwide [3,4]. The first case of COVID-19 infection in Kuwait was detected in the last week of February 2020, and at the time of this study, the national death toll had reached 2,452. The cumulative number of cases in Kuwait reported an alarming number of approximately 411,981[5].

Front-line workers, including medical staff, police officers, volunteers, community workers, and journalists, have played a significant role in stressful times to effectively control the spread of COVID-19 [6]. A recent report from Germany mentioned that around 4398 healthcare professionals had contracted COVID-19 [7]. This high rate of infection and mortality involves an unprecedented impact on the healthcare organization's performance. Maslach et al. described burnout as a state of psychological, emotional, and physical stress that responds to some degree of exposure to occupational stress [8]. This response has three key dimensions: overwhelming exhaustion, cynicism and detachment from the job, and a sense of effectiveness and failure. Occupational burnout can have significant negative long-time consequences among patients and front-line workers. It results in low physical and mental strain, lack of motivation, absenteeism, and poor morale among workers, leading to a deterioration of the quality of health care services [9].

Several literature reviews have shown a relationship between high levels of burnout in healthcare professionals and well-being in inpatient care [9,10]. These consequences impose high physical, psychosocial, and financial costs on society [11]. The deadly and infectious nature of COVID-19 poses an additional risk of transmission to front-line workers, which eventually provokes anxiety and stress. Front-line workers experienced social stigmatization, shortage of personal protection equipment supplies, interpersonal isolation, and heavy workload during the COVID-19 outbreak. Therefore, this pandemic has been reported to have a substantial psychological impact on Healthcare personnel [12]. According to Amnesty International, up to now, at least 17,000 front-line health workers have died worldwide from COVID-19 over the last year while also calling for a rapid vaccine release to protect millions of front-line healthcare workers [13]. Several studies have revealed that some depression symptoms contribute substantially to emotional exhaustion [14]. Poor mental state can seriously affect front-line staff's decision-making, mental concentration, and execution, which would hinder the fight against the COVID-19 epidemic and might even cause permanent physical and psychological injury to front-line personals [15]. Consequently, it is essential to measure and monitor the fatigue and psychological status of the front-line staff.

Therefore, we decided to conduct a study to explore the level of burnout in front-line workers during the COVID-19 pandemic in Kuwait and examine factors associated with the development of this psychological sequel. We are motivated to explore an efficient feature selection approach with practical machine learning and deep learning methodologies to predict early job burnout prerequisites in Kuwait's front-line workers.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows: initially, we present an efficient feature subset selection approach using promising metaheuristic methods such as Bat, Cuckoo, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), and GWO to select the best features. We build a model using several classification approaches, including AnDE Bayesian, JChaid* decision tree, SVM margin-based, ForestPA Decision forest, and DMLP neural network on the reduced features. A new burnout dataset is gathered and implemented to study the effectiveness of the proposed job burnout detection system. To understand the efficacy of the proposed detection model, we consider several performance evaluation metrics. We compare the classification performance between machine and deep learning algorithms, especially with imbalanced and small datasets. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first study that focuses on analyzing job burnout datasets in the Arabic language using machine and deep learning techniques.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 explores an overview of the related work in applying machine learning in social and behavioral sciences. Section 3 describes the burnout measure and the gathered dataset. In Section 4, the proposed classification algorithms and feature selection techniques are more investigated. The results are discussed in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 introduces the conclusions.

II. RELATED RESEARCH

Machine learning is gaining popularity in social and behavioral sciences [16]. As, several algorithms were applied in computational psychiatry to improve the treatment of mental health, anxiety, and mood disorders such as stress [17], depression [18], Schizophrenia [19], and suicidality [20]. Machine learning algorithms played a role in analyzing data from different sources. For example, Silva and colleagues used machine learning techniques and wearable devices to build an Information System to monitor and assess stress during exams to help students manage their stress levels [17]. Likewise, Divya Nori proposed a mobile application based on LASSO-penalized Generalized

Linear, Gradient boosting, and feed-forward multilayer perceptron models to detect linguistic biomarkers of mood disorders in a teen's outgoing SMS messages and send notifications to a parent [21].

Several articles compared machine learning methods with conventional and statistical Methods. Mary & Jabasheela built a model to predict depression and mental illness using four machine learning algorithms and compared results with a logistic regression model. Results revealed that logistic regression achieved the highest Accuracy [22]. Kessler and colleagues (2016) studied the level of depression and predicted suicide cases after psychiatric hospitalization among US Army soldiers in the 12 months after hospital discharge. Results showed that the machine learning algorithms achieved better results than conventional techniques [20].

Different machine learning was used to identify the level of burnout syndrome. Lee et al. developed an app based on the convolutional neural network (CNN) to detect burnouts using the Maslach Burnout Inventory–Human Services Survey to help assess 1002 nurse burnouts working in a medical center in Taiwan at an earlier stage [23]. The results showed that the 20-item model and CNN helped improve prediction accuracy, which yielded a higher accuracy rate of 95%. Gen-Min et al. designed a Machine Learning Based model based on several classifiers to predict Suicide Ideation among Military Personnel. The results showed that they achieved an accuracy of 100% using multilayer perceptron and support vector machine algorithms. Taylor et al. built a well-being and mood model based on data collected from surveys, wearable sensors, smartphone logs, and the weather using deep neural networks, Multi-Kernel learning, and a Hierarchical Bayesian model [24]. The empirical results showed that considering individual differences using machine learning techniques resulted in significant performance improvements. Batata et al. proposed a mixed machine learning and agent-based simulation tool for detecting caregivers with severe burnout [25]. They collected data from caregivers using a self-estimation indicator and SRB burnout metric. Several classical machine learning methods were trained and tested using caregivers/patients collected data. Results showed that Neural Networks demonstrates the best results for burnout prediction and admission control policy [26].

III. JOB BURNOUT DATASET

A. Burnout Measure and Data Collection

To evaluate the status of job burnout and its impact on working ability among medical staff and police officers, we choose Maslach burnout inventory—Human Services Survey (MBI-HSS) as it is considered to be the most trustworthy and the most common tool of this kind [27]. First, the survey starts with collecting the demographic data, including socio-demographic (gender, age, marital status, education level) and occupational (Education level, Marital status, Professional experience, workplace, job satisfaction) factors. Second, the other part was a web-based Arabic validated version of MBI-HSS [28].

The MBI-HSS instrument comprises 22 items (Q1 to Q22; we refer the reader to [28] for more details). The questionnaires are ranked on a 7-point Likert scale from 0 (“never”) to 6 (“daily”). According to the critical values, job burnout was divided into four levels: zero, mild, moderate, and high burnout. The Arabic MBI-HSS evaluation results for occupational groups showed that the scale was reliable and valid [29]. At present, the MBI-HSS instrument has been widely used in healthcare and social workers, police, university students, and other professional fields [23,30].

B. General Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

The participants were required to be part of the police personnel and healthcare workers currently on duty in Kuwait to be included in the study, from which 599 people completed the MBI-HSS questionnaire. The MBI-HSS questionnaire was circulated in Arabic to front-line personnel from 31 December 2020 to 7 March 2021. Table 1 illustrates the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. Two hundred seventy-seven were men (46%), and 322 were women (54%). Furthermore, there was a significant number of participants who were healthcare workers (68%). Most were younger than 40 years (67%) and had a college degree or above (96%). Regarding marital status, many participants were married (73%), and most of the participants were generally satisfied with their job (93%). We noted that of all the participants who had completed the MBI-HSS questionnaire, 91% of them had experienced moderate levels of professional burnout (Table 2). The first glance of the analysis dataset demonstrated that mild to moderate burnout exists in the front-line personnel in Kuwait during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 1
The Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Items	Group	Case Numbers	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	277	46
	Female	322	54
Age	25~	130	22
	30~	172	29
	35~	98	16
	40~	97	16
	> 45	102	17
Education level	Highschool	28	4
	Bachelor	308	51
	Diploma	91	15
	>	172	29
Marital status	Married	436	73
	Unmarried	163	27
Professional experience (years)	<5	116	19
	5~	116	19
	10~	101	17
	15~	266	44
Occupation	Law-enforcement	189	32
	Healthcare	410	68
Job satisfaction	Yes	560	93
	No	39	7
Total		599	100%

Table 2
Detection Rate of Job Burnout

Burnout level	Case Number	Percentage (%)
Mild burnout	56	9
Moderate burnout	543	91

IV. CLASSIFICATION AND FEATURE SELECTION METHODS

The process of feature selection is about selecting distinctive features and excluding irrelevant and redundant ones. The reduction of features aims to find the basic feature set, and this ultimately enhances the classification accuracy by reducing the processing time. Most datasets contain plenty of unnecessary attributes, which lower data mining algorithms' efficacy [31]. This research aims to investigate which factors contribute the most to the prediction of job burnout. Therefore, we decided to study the performance of several metaheuristic optimization-based feature selection approaches with several classifiers. This section discusses the applied machine learning classifiers and chaotic grey wolf optimization algorithm in detecting job burnout.

1. AnDE algorithm

AnDE (Averaged n-dependence Estimator) is a class of Bayesian algorithms based on Naïve Bayes (NB) learning and known for its capabilities to handle missing values and learn from training samples in a single pass permit out-of-core learning. AnDE has a lower bias as it allows every attribute to depend on n shared super parent attributes at the cost of high variance. AnDE has many good features, such as no model selection is needed and requiring parameter tuning and direct prediction of class probabilities [32,33]. AnDE maintains the desirable and valuable properties of NB with minimum computational overheads and substantial predictive Accuracy. The applied AnDE algorithm, with $n = 2$, starts with initializing the number of records, constants, probability estimation values, and the joint frequency values in the training phase. Then, the A2DE classifier predicts the class by even outsourcing one dependence estimator to the number of records available in the dataset in the prediction phase.

2. JChaid* algorithm

JChaid* [34] is an improved decision tree algorithm from CHI-square Automatic Interaction Detection (CHAID) decision tree algorithm. The automated classification model is built on the co-relationships between the predictor class variable and dependent variables. The original CHAID algorithm was a non-parametric was proposed by Gordon V. Kass [35]. It works by considering the F-statistical in examining the relationship between a class predictor and a dependent variable. Compared with other decision tree algorithms, JChaid* can deal with noisy and imbalanced datasets since it splits the nodes in multiway while building the decision tree model to avoid the overfitting difficulty.

C. SVM classifier

SVM (Support Vector Machine) is a statistical learning theory invented by Vapnik [36], and since then, it has become a popular tool for solving several classification tasks as it has reported good classification accuracy in

many pattern recognition problems [37]. The SVM algorithm works through mapping the original input space into a dot product space-based dimension and calls it to feature-space, and accordingly, the discriminant hyperplane is constructed. The discriminant hyperplane is defined by exploiting the optimization theory and respecting insights provided by the statistical learning theory. We proceed with classification using SVM with Polynomial Kernel Function.

D. ForestPA Classifier

Unlike other algorithms that use a subset of the non-class attributes, Forest by Penalizing Attributes (ForestPA) builds a set of highly accurate decision trees by exploiting the strength of all non-class attributes available in a dataset [38]. Simultaneously, some weight-related concerns, such as weight assignment and weight increment strategies, are considered to retain individual accuracy and promote substantial diversity. ForestPA is constructed by penalizing attributes that are used in previous trees in a decision forest. ForestPA randomly selects the weight of a feature from the weight range allocated for the attribute's level. Furthermore, ForestPA enforces weights such that an attribute tested at a lower level receives a lower weight/higher penalty than an attribute tested at a higher level.

E. DMLP

Deep Learning via Multilayer Perception (DMLP), also known as a deep feed-forward neural network, is considered an archetypal deep learning model where a backpropagation neural network trains the model with deep multilayers [39]. DMLP uses Limited-Memory Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno (L-BFGS) algorithm as an optimization routine. Several parameters should be considered before building a DMLP classifier, such as the number of hidden layers, batch size, successful activation functions, seed size, loss function, and convergence tolerance [40]. The performance of the DMLP mainly depends upon the optimum hyperparameter setting and the size of the training data. The motivation behind proposing a deep learning classifier is to compare its performance in dealing with small datasets with other classifiers.

F. CGWO

The Chaotic Grey Wolf Optimization Algorithm (CGWO) algorithm is mainly motivated by the natural leadership and hunting behaviors of grey wolves, which most prefer to live in a pack [41]. Each herd has four foremost ranks that are modeled as four categories: alpha (α), beta (β), delta (δ) and omega (ω) [42]. The second inspiration for GWO comes from the group-hunting behavior to catch prey in nature. The hunting mechanism starts with tracking the prey, then chasing and harassing until it finally stops moving before attacking. According to the GWO algorithm, the alpha, beta, and delta represent the first, second, third-best solutions. The remaining candidate solutions are regarded as omegas. The hunting process of the grey wolves can be mathematically modeled as:

$$\vec{D} = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}_p - \vec{X}(t)| \quad , \quad 1$$

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = |\vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D}|$$

Where \vec{X} and \vec{X}_p represent the prey and grey wolf positions at an iteration (t), respectively. \vec{A} and \vec{C} are coefficient vectors that can be formulated as follows:

$$\vec{A} = |2a \cdot \overrightarrow{rand_1} - \vec{a}| \quad , \quad 2$$

$$\vec{C} = 2 \cdot \overrightarrow{rand_2}$$

Where $\overrightarrow{rand_1}$ and $\overrightarrow{rand_2}$ are random vectors in [0,1]. \vec{a} is linearly decreasing from 2 to zero over iterations as follows:

$$a = 2 - t * \frac{2}{iterations} \quad 3$$

Simulation experiments for the chaotic grey wolf optimization algorithm had proved that the Chebyshev map would perform better than other chaotic methods [42]:

$$x_{i+1} = \cos\left(\frac{\alpha}{\cos x_i}\right) \quad 4$$

In this paper, we set the default value of parameter $\alpha = 0.7$ and chose chaos generated by Chebyshev mapping to replace all random numbers in the Gauss distribution in the GWO.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When learning from a small amount of imbalanced data, performance metrics usually favors the majority class. Therefore, we decided first to split the training and testing datasets using 10-fold cross-validation. Then we applied more appropriate measures for imbalanced datasets such as sensitivity (recall), specificity, accuracy, precision, and *f*-measure [43]. According to the confusion matrix of a two-class problem, the main formulations are defined in Equations 5-9. Where TP indicates the number of true positives, FN indicates the number of false negatives, TN indicates the number of true negatives, and FP indicates the number of false positives.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + FN + TN} \quad 5$$

Consequently, we can define Precision, Sensitivity and specificity as

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{FP + TP} \quad 6$$

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad 7$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad 8$$

The *f*-measure is used as it measures the harmonic mean of the classifier's Precision, and Sensitivity as

$$f\text{-measure} = \frac{TP}{TP + \frac{1}{2}(FP + FN)} \quad 9$$

To test the effectiveness and the strength of our proposed technique will be thoroughly investigated by using several classifiers and feature selection techniques. We decided to compare the performance of the proposed algorithm with other well-regarded metaheuristic feature selection algorithms, namely: Bat, Cuckoo, PSO, and GWO algorithms.

The objective of the feature selection phase is to accomplish a dramatic reduction in feature numbers by minimizing the number of selected features to maximize classification accuracy. These reductions are attributed to the new proposed score vector, which considers the correlations among different combinations of variables and ensures only minimal variable-variable correlations and maximum variable-class correlations remain for data processing. This process allows us to reduce the number of features used in classification with little effect on the accuracy of the predictive models.

Table 3 list the optimal number of features using state-of-the-art metaheuristic techniques and CGWO. Figure 1 illustrates the percentage reduction in the number of features selected by each feature selection method. Here we can notice that all the feature selection methods helped reduce the number of features from 29 to 6-10. CGWO method substantially reduced the search space of the selected features compared with the results produced by Ant, Bat, Cuckoo, PSO, and GWO. We can see that the CGWO algorithm obtained the lowest number of features.

The Venn diagram in Figure 2 illustrates the overlapping and exclusive features in each feature selection group. Table 4 gives a more detailed view of the mutual features. We applied the Venn diagram to indicate the differences among the techniques. We found that all the feature techniques shared a total of 6 features. Bat, CGWO, Cuckoo, GWO, and PSO techniques share four features, while Bat Cuckoo GWO PSO shares five features. As illustrated above, the results proved that CGWO is more proficient than GWO in reducing feature numbers. The feature reduction results indicate that demographic variables were non-significant on the prevalence of burnout. Moreover, results showed no significant relationship between job satisfaction and burnout as most of the sample (93%) were satisfied with their job.

Table 3
Selected Features

Feature Selection	Selected Features	Total
Bat	Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, Q5, Q6, Q7, Q9, Q11, Q15, Q16, Q17	12
Cuckoo	Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, Q5, Q6, Q7, Q9, Q15, Q16, Q17, Q18, Q20	13
PSO	Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, Q5, Q6, Q7, Q8, Q15, Q17	10
GWO	Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, Q5, Q6, Q7, Q15, Q17	9
CGWO	Q1, Q2, Q3, Q9, Q16, Q17	6

Figure 1 Reduction in the number of features (given in percentage) for each method

Figure 2 Venn diagram of the feature selection techniques

Table 4
Optimal number of features

Feature Selection Technique	Total	Elements
Bat, CGWO, Cuckoo, GWO, PSO	4	Q3 Q2 Q1 Q17
Bat, Cuckoo, GWO, PSO	5	Q7 Q4 Q5 Q15 Q6
Bat, CGWO, Cuckoo	2	Q16 Q9
Bat	1	Q11
Cuckoo	2	Q18 Q20
PSO	1	Q8

To validate this finding, we decided to check the predictive models' performance based on the classification algorithms AnDE Bayesian, JChaid* decision tree, SVM margin-based, ForestPA Decision forest, and DMLP classifiers before and after applying the metaheuristic techniques on the dataset. A summary of the classifier's setting included is presented in Table 5.

Table 6 shows the results of the predictive models before applying the reduction methods. Bold values indicate the best results in the table. The results indicate that SVM and DMLP classifiers scored the best classification results, whereas the JChaid* classifier has lower classification results than other algorithms. As shown in Table 5, Accuracy, Specificity, Precision, and *f*-measure accomplished with the SVM classifier were equal to 0.977, 0.998, 0.977, and 0.854, respectively. These results were comparatively better than the other classifiers acquired. The accuracies of the classifiers laid in the interval [0.918–0.975] as 0.933, 0.918, 0.945, and 0.975 for the JChaid*, AnDE, ForestPA, and DMLP classifiers, respectively. According to precision, specificity, *f*-measure, and accuracy criteria, SVM preserved leadership in its classification capacity.

Table 5
Classifiers' parameter settings

Classifier	Details
JChaid*	batchSize= 100 confidence factor = 0.25 significance level = 0.05
A2DE	batchSize= 100
DMLP	Output layer: Activation Function Sigmoid Hidden layer: Logistic activation function loss function: Squared error for MLP Classifier tolerance parameter for the delta values = 1E-06 number of hidden units = 2 batch size = 100
SVM	The kernel: polynomial Degree (d) : 1, 2, 3 Gamma in Kernel functions (Y) : 0.1, 0.2,0.3.....2.0 Regularization (C): 1,10,100,1000 Tolerance = 0.001
ForestPA	batchSize= 100 simpleCartPruningFolds=2 simpleCartMinimumRecords=2 numberOfTrees=10

Table 6
Results for classification performance for Job burnout dataset

Type of Learning	Classifier	Accuracy	Specificity	Precision	Sensitivity	f-measure
Machine Learning	JChaid*	0.933	0.983	0.735	0.446	0.536
	AnDE	0.918	0.937	0.547	0.732	0.607
	ForestPA	0.945	0.996	0.926	0.446	0.589
	SVM	0.977	0.998	0.977	0.768	0.854
Deep Learning	DMLP	0.975	0.994	0.936	0.786	0.847

Table 7 presents the results of comparing the two algorithms (GWO, CGWO) with the other metaheuristic algorithms. Figures 3 and 4 show the boxplots for the performance of the search techniques and the classification schemes, based on the accuracy metric, in which it visually plots for each boxplot: minimum, maximum, median, first quartile, and third quartile values of the data. The line inside the box indicates the median value. We have noticed that the PSO algorithm has higher boxplots compared to the other algorithms. Also, the median of the proposed algorithm has a more exceptional value compared to the remaining algorithms. Overall, the second-best

algorithm is GWO, while Bat is the runner-up in median value. Overall, the box plots allow us to observe that CGWO is competitive. As can be seen, GWO performs better than CGWO with a more significant number of features.

Nevertheless, results show that CGWO is superior in reducing the dimensionality of the job burnout dataset by selecting fewer features than the rest of the methods. However, the difference between BAT and Cuckoo, GWO as we give more attention to the number of features selected rather than the classification accuracy. Thus, the classification accuracy is affected by the number of selected features. The CGWO technique shows highly competitive results regardless of the classifier used. We can conclude from all these experiments that reducing the number of features allows for a better understanding of the underlying model used to make predictions.

Figure 4 presents the boxplot of the accuracy scores of the machine learning models on the job burnout dataset. The accuracies for all of the machine learning methods are over 91%. The accuracy results of JChaid* range from 0.923 to 0.954. AnDE has accuracy outcomes that range from 0.928 to 0.980. The accuracy results of the ForestPA classifier range from 0.928 to 0.957. SVM Classifier accuracy results range from 0.925 to 0.963. The accuracy results of DMLP range from 0.927 to 0.957.

The impact of reduction methods on the predictive performance results is noticeable. For instance, when the AnDE algorithm was applied, it had higher predictive power when feature selection techniques were applied. Results support that DMLP is better than other classifiers such as JChaid*, AnDE, and ForestPA when the dataset is small. It bears mentioning, DMLP has achieved the second-highest f-measure, which is desirable when a data set is unbalanced. Thus, experimental results support the adaptation of deep learning architectures in social sciences when data is relatively small.

The compared outcome clearly shows that the SVM and AnDE algorithms have comparatively higher accuracy than the existing method. As a final note, although DMLP is effective in modeling nonlinear data for classification purposes, they underperformed relative to most other machine learning classifiers employed in this work. This may be explained because the dataset size is small (599 records) than what DMLP requires. Therefore, a more extensive data set is required to achieve better mapping and learning with DMLP, unlike all other classifiers, such as SVM, robust even when the data size is small and holds suitable generalization capability [36].

After the feature selection results, we agree with the conclusion by [44] and [45] that the demographic variables do not affect job burnout status. Also, we agree with our colleagues in [46] that no significant relationship between job satisfaction and burnout was observed during the study of job burnout among nurses in the Intensive Care Unit.

In general, the results confirmed that mild to moderate burnout exists among the front-line personnel in Kuwait; therefore, calls for interventional actions are mostly needed to prevent and lower the level of burnout. The findings may considerably help to screen out the front-line workers at high risk for job burnout. Also, it can be generalized to develop a robust CAD-based tool as it requires fewer parameters than the original MBI-HSS questionnaire. Such an app may help self-assess job burnout early and subsequently protect and support front-line workers during this pandemic.

Table 7
Results for classification performance for Job burnout dataset after Feature Selection

Ant						
Type of Learning	Classifier	Accuracy	Specificity	Precision	Sensitivity	f-measure
Machine Learning	JChaid*	0.923	0.923	0.923	0.923	0.923
	AnDE	0.942	0.942	0.942	0.942	0.942
	ForestPA	0.937	0.989	0.800	0.429	0.540
	SVM	0.937	0.987	0.781	0.446	0.550
Deep Learning	DMLP	0.940	0.987	0.794	0.482	0.583
Bat						
Machine Learning	JChaid*	0.923	0.938	0.923	0.938	0.923
	AnDE	0.967	0.969	0.967	0.969	0.967
	ForestPA	0.948	0.991	0.857	0.536	0.645
	SVM	0.937	0.987	0.781	0.446	0.550
Deep Learning	DMLP	0.943	0.987	0.806	0.518	0.614
Cuckoo						
Machine Learning	JChaid*	0.954	0.978	0.692	0.643	0.654
	AnDE	0.942	0.967	0.684	0.696	0.674
	ForestPA	0.957	0.996	0.941	0.571	0.700
	SVM	0.963	0.991	0.886	0.696	0.769
Deep Learning	DMLP	0.957	0.989	0.857	0.643	0.722
PSO						
Machine Learning	JChaid*	0.933	0.940	0.933	0.940	0.933
	AnDE	0.980	0.971	0.980	0.971	0.980
	ForestPA	0.952	0.994	0.909	0.536	0.661
	SVM	0.937	0.987	0.781	0.446	0.550
Deep Learning	DMLP	0.940	0.987	0.794	0.482	0.583
GWO						
Machine Learning	JChaid*	0.913	0.912	0.913	0.912	0.913
	AnDE	0.965	0.950	0.965	0.950	0.965

	ForestPA	0.927	0.989	0.750	0.321	0.430
	SVM	0.923	0.989	0.727	0.286	0.390
Deep Learning	DMLP	0.927	0.980	0.676	0.411	0.489
EGWO						
	JChaid*	0.928	0.974	0.659	0.482	0.535
	AnDE	0.928	0.980	0.686	0.429	0.506
	ForestPA	0.928	0.993	0.810	0.304	0.424
	SVM	0.925	0.996	0.867	0.232	0.351
Deep Learning	DMLP	0.928	0.991	0.783	0.321	0.437

Figure 3 Boxplot for the feature selection techniques based on Accuracy

Figure 4 Boxplot for the classification schemes based on Accuracy

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Our study uses machine learning techniques to predict job burnout of front-line personnel during the COVID-19 pandemic in Kuwait. We started with gathering the burnout responses provided by 599 police personnel and

healthcare workers. Then, we utilize five machine learning techniques and six metaheuristic methods to explore features. Our model has been trained and tested on a small dataset. The experimental results showed that the techniques of PSO and GWO provide the best performance for the feature selection as the classification performance is affected by the number of selected features. Results support that DMLP is better than other classifiers such as JChaid*, AnDE, and ForestPA when the dataset is small. This research encourages the author to investigate further the adequacy of the proposed approach with unlike datasets.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the author upon reasonable request.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Jin, C., Chen, W., Cao, Y., Xu, Z., Zhang, X., Deng, L., Zheng, C., Zhou, J., Shi, H. and Feng, J., Development and evaluation of an AI system for COVID-19 diagnosis. medRxiv 2020. preprint [https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.20.20039834].
- [2] World Health Organization (2020b) Covid-19 weekly epidemiological update. www.who.int/publications/m/item/weekly-epidemiological-update---17-november-2020. Accessed 21 Nov 2020
- [3] Barello, S., Falcó-Pegueroles, A., Rosa, D., Tolotti, A., Graffigna, G. and Bonetti, L., 2020. The psychosocial impact of flu influenza pandemics on healthcare workers and lessons learnt for the COVID-19 emergency: a rapid review. *International journal of public health*, pp.1-12.
- [4] Sim, K. and Chua, H.C., 2004. The psychological impact of SARS: a matter of heart and mind. *Cmaj*, 170(5), pp.811-812.
- [5] World Health Organization 2020a, <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>
- [6] Draper, H., Wilson, S., Ives, J., Gratus, C., Greenfield, S., Parry, J., Petts, J. and Sorell, T., 2008. Healthcare workers' attitudes towards working during pandemic influenza: a multi method study. *BMC Public Health*, 8(1), pp.1-7.
- [7] Nienhaus, A. and Hod, R., 2020. COVID-19 among health workers in Germany and Malaysia. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(13), p.4881.
- [8] Maslach, C. and Jackson, S.E., 1996. *Leiter MP Maslach burnout inventory manual*. Palo Alto: California Consulting Psychological Press Inc.
- [9] Dewa, C.S., Jacobs, P., Thanh, N.X. and Loong, D., 2014. An estimate of the cost of burnout on early retirement and reduction in clinical hours of practicing physicians in Canada. *BMC Health Services Research*, 14(1), pp.1-9.
- [10] Hall, L.H., Johnson, J., Watt, I., Tsipa, A. and O'Connor, D.B., 2016. Healthcare staff wellbeing, burnout, and patient safety: a systematic review. *PloS one*, 11(7), p.e0159015.
- [11] Shanafelt, T.D., Dyrbye, L.N., West, C.P. and Sinsky, C.A., 2016, November. Potential impact of burnout on the US physician workforce. In *Mayo Clinic Proceedings* (Vol. 91, No. 11, p. 1667). Elsevier Limited.
- [12] Guo, J., Liao, L., Wang, B., Li, X., Guo, L., Tong, Z., Guan, Q., Zhou, M., Wu, Y., Zhang, J. and Gu, Y., 2020. Psychological effects of COVID-19 on hospital staff: a national cross-sectional survey of China mainland. Available at SSRN 3550050.
- [13] World Health Organization, 2021. The impact of COVID-19 on health and care workers: a closer look at deaths (No. WHO/HWF/WorkingPaper/2021.1). World Health Organization.
- [14] Robinson, R.L., Stephenson, J.J., Dennehy, E.B., Grabner, M., Faries, D., Palli, S.R. and Swindle, R.W., 2015. The importance of unresolved fatigue in depression: costs and comorbidities. *Psychosomatics*, 56(3), pp.274-285.
- [15] Liu, S., Yang, L., Zhang, C., Xiang, Y.T., Liu, Z., Hu, S. and Zhang, B., 2020. Online mental health services in China during the COVID-19 outbreak. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(4), pp.e17-e18.
- [16] DelPozo-Banos, M., John, A., Petkov, N., Berridge, D.M., Southern, K., LLoyd, K., Jones, C., Spencer, S. and Travieso, C.M., 2018. Using neural networks with routine health records to identify suicide risk: feasibility study. *JMIR mental health*, 5(2), p.e10144.
- [17] Silva, E., Aguiar, J., Reis, L.P., e Sá, J.O., Gonçalves, J. and Carvalho, V., 2020. Stress among Portuguese medical students: the eustress solution. *Journal of medical systems*, 44(2), pp.1-6.
- [18] Webb, C.A., Cohen, Z.D., Beard, C., Forgeard, M., Peckham, A.D. and Björgvinsson, T., 2020. Personalized prognostic prediction of treatment outcome for depressed patients in a naturalistic psychiatric hospital setting: A comparison of machine learning approaches. *Journal of consulting and clinical psychology*, 88(1), p.25.
- [19] Krystal, J.H., Murray, J.D., Chekroud, A.M., Corlett, P.R., Yang, G., Wang, X.J. and Anticevic, A., 2017. Computational psychiatry and the challenge of schizophrenia.

- [20] Kessler, R.C., van Loo, H.M., Wardenaar, K.J., Bossarte, R.M., Brenner, L.A., Cai, T., Ebert, D.D., Hwang, I., Li, J., de Jonge, P. and Nierenberg, A.A., 2016. Testing a machine-learning algorithm to predict the persistence and severity of major depressive disorder from baseline self-reports. *Molecular psychiatry*, 21(10), pp.1366-1371.
- [21] Nori, D., 2020. iSense: AI-Based Model and App to Identify Linguistic Biomarkers of Mood Disorders.
- [22] Mary, S.A. and Jabasheela, L., 2018, February. An evaluation of classification techniques for depression, anxiety and stress assessment. In *International Conference for phoenixes on emerging current trends in engineering and management (PECTEAM 2018)* (pp. 64-69). Atlantis Press.
- [23] Lee, Y.L., Chou, W., Chien, T.W., Chou, P.H., Yeh, Y.T. and Lee, H.F., 2020. An app developed for detecting nurse burnouts using the convolutional neural networks in Microsoft Excel: population-based questionnaire study. *JMIR medical informatics*, 8(5), p.e16528.
- [24] Taylor, S., Jaques, N., Nosakhare, E., Sano, A. and Picard, R., 2017. Personalized multitask learning for predicting tomorrow's mood, stress, and health. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 11(2), pp.200-213.
- [25] Batata, O., Augusto, V. and Xie, X., 2018, December. Mixed machine learning and agent-based simulation for respite care evaluation. In *2018 Winter Simulation Conference (WSC)* (pp. 2668-2679). IEEE.
- [26] Lin, G.M., Nagamine, M., Yang, S.N., Tai, Y.M., Lin, C. and Sato, H., 2020. Machine learning based suicide ideation prediction for military personnel. *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics*, 24(7), pp.1907-1916.
- [27] Lheureux, F., Borteyrou, X. and Truchot, D., 2017. The Maslach Burnout Inventory–Human Services Survey (MBI-HSS): Factor Structure, Wording Effect and Psychometric. *Le Travail Humain*, 80(2), pp.29-54.
- [28] Sabbah I, Sabbah H, Sabbah S, Akoum H, Droubi N. Burnout among Lebanese nurses: psychometric properties of the Maslach burnout inventory-human services survey (MBI-HSS). *Health*. 2012;04(09):644–52.
- [29] Ibtissam, S., Hala, S., Sanaa, S., Hussein, A. and Nabil, D., 2012. Burnout among Lebanese nurses: Psychometric properties of the Maslach burnout inventory-human services survey (MBI-HSS). *Health*, 2012.
- [30] Grządzielewska, M., 2021. Using machine learning in burnout prediction: A survey. *Child and Adolescent Social Work Journal*, 38(2), pp.175-180.
- [31] Saranya, G. and Pravin, A., 2021. Feature Selection Techniques for Disease Diagnosis System: A Survey. In *Artificial Intelligence Techniques for Advanced Computing Applications* (pp. 249-258). Springer, Singapore.
- [32] S. Chen, A. M. Martínez, G. I. Webb, and L. Wang, "Selective AnDE for large data learning: A low-bias memory constrained approach," *Knowl. Inf. Syst.*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 475–503, Feb. 2017.
- [33] G.I.Webb,J.R.Boughton,F.Zheng,K.M.Ting,andH.Salem,"Learning by extrapolation from marginal to full-multivariate probability distributions: Decreasingly naive Bayesian classification," *Mach. Learn.*, vol. 86, no. 2, pp. 233–272, Feb. 2012.
- [34] Ibarguren, A. Lasarguren, J. M. Pérez, J. Muguerza, I. Gurrutxaga, and O. Arbelaitz, "BFPART: Best-first PART," *Inf. Sci.*, vols. 367–368, pp. 927–952, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ins.2016.07.023.
- [35] G. V. Kass, "An exploratory technique for investigating large quantities of categorical data," *J. Roy. Stat. Soc. C, Appl. Statist.*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp.119–127, 1980. [Online]. Available: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2986296>
- [36] Vapnik, V., Guyon, I. and Hastie, T., 1995. Support vector machines. *Mach. Learn*, 20(3), pp.273-297.
- [37] Cervantes, J., Garcia-Lamont, F., Rodríguez-Mazahua, L. and Lopez, A., 2020. A comprehensive survey on support vector machine classification: Applications, challenges and trends. *Neurocomputing*, 408, pp.189-215.
- [38] Adnan, M.N. and Islam, M.Z., 2017. Forest PA: Constructing a decision forest by penalizing attributes used in previous trees. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 89, pp.389-403.
- [39] Wan, S., Liang, Y., Zhang, Y. and Guizani, M., 2018. Deep multi-layer perceptron classifier for behavior analysis to estimate parkinson's disease severity using smartphones. *IEEE Access*, 6, pp.36825-36833.
- [40] Fang, R., Sondak, D., Protopapas, P. and Succi, S., 2018. Deep learning for turbulent channel flow. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1812.02241*.
- [41] Mehak K and Sankalap A 2018 Chaotic grey wolf optimization algorithm for constrained optimization problems *Journal of Computational Design and Engineering* 5 (4) 458-472.
- [42] Kohli, M. and Arora, S., 2018. Chaotic grey wolf optimization algorithm for constrained optimization problems. *Journal of computational design and engineering*, 5(4), pp.458-472.
- [43] Bekkar, M., Djemaa, H.K. and Alitouche, T.A., 2013. Evaluation measures for models assessment over imbalanced data sets. *J Inf Eng Appl*, 3(10).
- [44] ZAREI, M.H., SEYED, K.N. and AKHAVAN, A.M.R., 2012. Do demographic variables moderate the relationship between job burnout and its consequences?.
- [45] Madan, P. and Srivastava, S., 2015. Employee engagement, job satisfaction and demographic relationship: An empirical study of private sector bank managers. *FIIB Business Review*, 4(2), pp.53-62.
- [46] Saeidi, R., Izanloo, A. and Izanlou, S., 2020. A study of the relationship between job satisfaction and burnout among neonatal intensive care unit staff. *Iranian Journal of Neonatology IJN*, 11(1), pp.67-70.